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Energy Demand Estimation for Shoreside Power Supply to Vessels Queued for Berthing at Brazilian Ports

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Abstract

The maritime sector is pursuing decarbonization, addressing emissions not only during sailing but also while vessels are idle at port. Methods to calculate port energy demand for onshore power supply have not yet been applied in Brazilian ports, and this article seeks to fill that gap with a framework adapted to the national context. The aim of this study is to estimate the electrical demand required to provide shore-side power to vessels queued at berth for the Port of Rio de Janeiro, supporting infrastructure planning and promoting sustainable operations through reduced emissions and fuel consumption. By combining Automatic Identification System (AIS) data with ship characteristics databases, average waiting times and power consumption profiles were estimated. A risk-based analysis of minimum demand requirements guided the definition of infrastructure scenarios, with the 10th percentile threshold (37,914 MJ) selected as the most reliable reference to ensure operational continuity. This study demonstrates a scalable AIS-based framework for estimating port energy demand and identifies auxiliary engines as the primary target for decarbonization, setting a benchmark for sustainable port management in Brazil and beyond.

1 Introduction

1.1 General context

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are one of the climate change's drivers. Climate change is a consequence of the increase in atmospheric temperature, which is directly correlated with GHG emission as can be seen in Figure 1. If the increase in CO_2 emissions continues, the $1.5^\circ C$ threshold may be surpassed. In contrast, drastic emission cuts increase the chances of keeping warming close to this limit.

It is important to emphasize that emissions not only raise the average atmospheric temperature but also increase its variability. That is, the frequency of extreme weather will increase, including heatwaves and cold spells, as well as severe floods and droughts, according to IPCC (2018). For that reason, all industrial sectors are engaged in efforts to reduce their emissions.

Among the various industrial sectors, mar-

Figure 1: Correlation between GHG emissions and the increase in the average atmospheric temperature (Source: IPCC (2018)).

itime transport is the most efficient transport mode in terms of emissions per ton of transported goods. It handles around 80% of global cargo transport and produces approximately 2.89% of global GHG emissions Faber et al. (2020). Despite its efficiency, these emissions are significant, which is why efforts to reduce them are crucial.

Currently, the primary fuel used in cargo ships is bunker fuel — a low-quality, heavy oil that contains significant amounts of sulfur, further contributing to environmental harm. In response to this, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has established clear emission reduction targets (Faber et al., 2020):

- Reduce GHG emissions 20% - 30% by 2030, compared to 2008 levels;
- Reducing GHG emissions 70% - 80% by 2040, compared to 2008 levels;
- Achieve net-zero emissions by 2050.

To achieve IMO targets, several strategies are being analyzed to improve the energy efficiency of vessels, including enhancing hull hydrodynamics, utilizing lighter materials, and implementing new propulsion systems. Operational optimization, such as reducing cruising speeds, planning routes more efficiently, and adopting alternative fuels, is also considered.

These strategies are not applied in isolation; rather, the expectation is that a combination of these technologies will be implemented.

1.2 The role of the Ports in decarbonization

According to PIANC Portugal (2023), ports contribute to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in two main scopes:

1. **Direct emissions**, which originate from sources under the direct control of port authorities;
2. **Indirect emissions**, which are associated with the electricity purchased for use within the port, as well as other emissions that are not under the direct responsibility of the port authority but are linked to port operators. This category represents a significant share of the total, emissions chain, as it is related to third-party operations.

The participation of ports in the decarbonization process is essential to achieve global GHG emissions reduction targets, as well as to meet environmental goals, improve air and ocean quality, promote sustainable development, and attract investments.

In this context, ports must adopt effective decarbonization strategies, some of them could be:

- **Analysis of available emission reduction solutions**, including engagement with industry experts to identify technologically and economically viable alternatives.

- **Cost-benefit evaluation** of these solutions, focusing on their feasibility and planning a realistic and phased implementation roadmap.
- **Development of a residual emissions compensation plan**, targeting emissions that cannot be eliminated, through mechanisms such as carbon credits or reforestation.
- **Achieving a sustainable business model**, through the implementation of planned measures and monitoring their effectiveness using environmental and operational indicators.
- **Continuous monitoring and feedback**, updating the cycle with current data, ensuring necessary adjustments and promoting continuous improvement.

1.3 Main trends in Ports decarbonization

To address the energy transition and the reduction of GHG emissions, ports have identified several possible solutions that can be implemented either together or individually, aiming to achieve the greatest positive impact while minimizing costs. Some of these trends and solutions are explained below.

According to Moreno (2022), several measures can be implemented to reduce emissions in ports, including the adoption of alternative fuel sources, the electrification of specific equipment, and the optimization of supply chain operations. The Port of Rotterdam and the port of Antwerp-Bruges have been widely recognized as a reference model, having deployed multiple technologies to advance the energy transition process. These initiatives include the gradual replacement of oil and gas with low-pollution energy sources that are renewable, clean, and low in carbon emissions, such as photovoltaic systems and wind power plants. In fact, the port has already implemented an operational large-scale solar energy system. Furthermore, the port of Rotterdam is developing the H-Vision project, which aims to supply low-greenhouse-gas-emission energy by 2030. As noted in Moreno (2022), this project involves the use of blue hydrogen and residual gases as substitutes for natural gas. Meanwhile, in Brazil, the Port of Açú is following the example set by the Port of Rotterdam by advancing the deployment of green hydrogen as an energy source and electrifying its operations to replace diesel fuel, according to Reuters (2024). In addition, the port is also leading a carbon capture

project, which has already demonstrated positive results. This project is based on the conservation and restoration of native vegetation through the Caruara Reserve and the replanting of local species, contributing to the mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions in the port region. Thereby, these initiatives reinforce the strategic role of ports in the energy transition and the adoption of sustainable practices, serving as a benchmark for future adaptations in the global maritime sector.

1.4 Literature Review

The Automatic Identification System (AIS) has become an essential tool for monitoring maritime traffic, originally implemented as part of international safety measures (Perez et al., 2020). This technology enables continuous tracking of vessel information, providing detailed datasets with updates every 2 to 10 seconds. According to the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) Convention and the International Maritime Organization (IMO), only passenger ships or commercial vessels with a gross tonnage (GT) above 300 are required to transmit AIS data. The transmitted information typically includes the vessel’s IMO number, type, geographic position, and time stamps.

Beyond its safety applications, AIS data offer significant advantages for environmental studies. By enabling accurate estimation of navigation time, average speed, and fuel consumption, AIS provides reliable input for emission calculations. These operational parameters are then combined with emission factors defined by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (Naturvårdsverket) to quantify pollutant emissions in specific regions. Finally, the integration of these datasets into Geographic Information System (GIS) platforms allows spatial mapping of emissions, linking them to navigation routes and vessel categories. Finally, emission estimates are spatially mapped to specific segments of navigation routes using data analysis tools and Geographic Information System (GIS) software, as described in the report by Perez et al. (2020). In Figure 2, the workflow described in the previous paragraph is illustrated in greater detail. It can also be observed that certain vessel categories, such as military, fishing, and dredging vessels, do not transmit AIS data. These vessels were analyzed separately to prevent double-counting in the emission estimates.

The mathematical method presented in Perez et al. (2020) for calculating emissions from AIS-based activity data initially sought to determine operational hours directly from recorded times-

Figure 2: Data querying, analysis, and emission estimation workflow. Source: Perez et al. (2020).

tamps. However, due to data gaps, this approach tended to overestimate results. To address this limitation, vessels were mapped to their corresponding routes, and the operational duration was calculated by dividing the length of each route segment (in nautical miles) by the vessel’s average speed (in nautical miles per hour). The propulsion engine horsepower-hours ($Hp\text{-Hrs}$) were then calculated according to Equation (1):

$$Hp\text{-Hrs} = Hp \times En \times (St_2 - St_1) \quad (1)$$

where Hp is the rated propulsion engine power, En is the number of engines, and St_1 and St_2 represent the entry and exit timestamps for the analyzed route segment.

Using the annual activity estimate (AH), the annual emissions (AE) were then computed as:

$$AE = AH \times CF_1 \times LF \times EF \times CF_2 \quad (2)$$

where CF_1 is a unit conversion factor (0.741 kW/HP), LF is the engine load factor, EF is the emission factor (g/kW · h), and CF_2 is a conversion factor to express the results in tonnes per year. This approach ensured an accurate estimation of pollutant emissions, including NO_x , CO, NMVOC, SO_2 , NH_3 , PM_{10} , and $PM_{2.5}$, by accounting for vessel operational time, installed power, and fuel consumption.

Therefore, in Spiliopoulos et al. (2020), the method for calculating GHG emissions uses the following types of data:

1. **Automatic Identification System (AIS) data** from vessels located in the areas of interest, in this case, port zones.
2. **Information on ports of interest** obtained from the World Port Index, which provides data on the location and physical characteristics of major ports and terminals worldwide.
3. **Vessel size**, which can be measured in different units depending on the vessel type: *Gross Tonnage* (GT), *Deadweight Tonnage* (DWT), *Container Units* (TEU), and vessel length.
4. **Vessel type**, which, when cross-referenced with vessel dimension data, allows for the estimation of auxiliary engine power using the tables published in the Fourth IMO GHG Study 2020.
5. **Pollutant emission factors** published in the Fourth IMO GHG Study 2020.

After gathering these datasets, Spiliopoulos et al. (2020) calculates the emissions generated by the fleet of vessels using the following method:

- First, the obtained dataset undergoes a filtering process to remove erroneous and duplicate records. All data related to vessels with a Gross Tonnage (GT) of less than 10,000 are discarded, as well as data for vessels outside the areas of interest and for vessels with speeds greater than 0.5 knots, since these are considered to be in motion.
- Next, a process is carried out to estimate the location of the quay and the geometry of the port area. Using the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) algorithm, vessel positions are grouped into clusters, each representing a candidate berth, as illustrated in Figure 3. For each berth, the centroid, size, and orientation are calculated based on the average positions and headings of the vessels. Overlapping candidates are merged into a minimum bounding rectangle. The final result is a set of polygons defining operational areas and port berths.

Figure 3: Method for generating quays using the DBSCAN algorithm, from left to right. Source: Spiliopoulos et al. (2020)

- Finally, the last step in Spiliopoulos et al. (2020) is to calculate the emissions generated by vessels located within the quay areas previously delineated. For this purpose, the following mathematical formula, shown in Equation 3, is applied, where AE is the auxiliary engine power in kilowatts (kW), t is the operational time in hours, and FE_i is the pollutant-specific emission factor in tonnes per kilowatt-hour (t/kWh).

$$E_i = AE \times t \times FE_i \quad (3)$$

Therefore, in Spiliopoulos et al. (2020), the adopted approach separates the processing of historical data from real-time analysis in order to efficiently estimate vessel emissions.

According to the study by Gutierrez-Torrea et al. (2020), many emission calculation methods are based on estimated vessel routes; however, these are less accurate than route estimates derived from AIS data, which provide greater precision. However, one of the challenges associated with using AIS data is the huge volume of information generated, since each transmitted signal has an average interval of only six seconds. Therefore, the study highlights the need to employ Big Data techniques for effective data analysis. Furthermore, the study developed by Gutierrez-Torrea et al. (2020) indicates that vessels are equipped with two types of engines: the main engines, which are responsible for propulsion, and the auxiliary engines, which supply electrical power and support other functions onboard. For this purpose, the study developed a model to estimate the power output of each type of engine in the vessel, which is essential to accurately determine its emissions. In this way, the power consumed by the main engine at a given instant t can be estimated using the following equation:

$$P_{\text{transient}} = \frac{V_{\text{transient}}^3}{(V_{\text{design}} + V_{\text{safety}})^3} \times p \times P_{\text{installed}}, \quad (4)$$

where $V_{\text{transient}}$ is the current speed of the vessel - obtained from AIS data; V_{design} is the vessel's design maximum speed; V_{safety} is the safety margin - set to 0.5 *knots* — to compensate for AIS data inaccuracies; p is the engine load factor at the maximum continuous rating (MCR) - set at 0.8; and $P_{\text{installed}}$ is the installed engine power in *kW*.

The power of the auxiliary engine, on the other hand, is estimated according to the vessel's operational mode, which can be categorized as *Hotelling/Moored*, *Maneuvering*, or *Cruising*. This classification is determined by the vessel's current speed, also obtained from AIS data. The

methodology assumes that the vessel type and navigation status are essential parameters for this estimation, although these are not always accurate or complete in AIS datasets. Similar to the other two studies previously reviewed, Gutierrez-Torrea et al. (2020) emphasizes the need to refine the AIS datasets obtained. In other words, it is necessary to apply filtering, processing, and enrichment procedures to correct inaccuracies, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Schematic model of the emission calculation method. Source: Gutierrez-Torrea et al. (2020).

Consequently, to address these issues, this work employs a methodology based on Conditional Restricted Boltzmann Machines (CRBMs) to enhance clustering and prediction algorithms, thereby improving the quality of attributes such as main engine power, navigation status, and vessel category derived from navigation traces. The choice of (CRBMs) relies on their ability to treat AIS data as multidimensional time series and to identify phase behavior patterns within them, as illustrated in Figure 5. This approach enables time-insensitive predictive models to achieve higher accuracy.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the CRBMs operating model. Source: Gutierrez-Torrea et al. (2020).

According to Gutierrez-Torrea et al. (2020), implementing this method allowed the detection of 45% of emissions that had previously gone unnoticed. In addition, other information such as navigation status and vessel type can be predicted or corrected when missing or misrepresented in the original dataset.

1.5 Scientific Gap

Several studies have addressed shore-side power demand estimation in Brazilian ports. For instance, Mével (2022) focused on constructing annual load curves for moored vessels at the *Paranaquá* Container Terminal (TCP), considering factors such as vessel type, operational mode, and berth occupancy time, aiming to estimate energy demand for shore power infrastructure planning.

Similarly, Ferraz (2022) developed a bottom-up methodology to estimate energy demand and fuel consumption by vessels at berth across multiple Brazilian ports over a decade, utilizing AIS data to account for vessel arrivals and operational times.

Additionally, Sfair et al. (2025) conducted an analytical study on the viability and effectiveness of a shore power system at the Port of Santos, evaluating its capacity to reduce pollutant emissions and comparing environmental and economic benefits.

However, these studies primarily consider vessels already at berth and do not explicitly model queued vessels awaiting berthing. Furthermore, they often assume static vessel types or operational modes, limiting the applicability for real-time or high-resolution energy demand estimation. Consequently, there is a gap in research on estimating shoreside power demand for vessels in queuing conditions, considering dynamic operational parameters such as navigation status, arrival times, and vessel type diversity. This study addresses this gap by integrating AIS-based vessel trajectories, operational modes, and queuing dynamics to provide a high-resolution estimate of energy demand.

1.6 Scientific relevance and purpose

This study contributes to filling a significant gap in the literature regarding the estimation of shore power demand for vessels at anchorage or scheduled to berth, a scenario that is still insufficiently investigated in Brazilian ports. By integrating AIS-based vessel trajectories, operational modes, and queuing dynamics, it provides a high-resolution and accurate model for energy demand estimation. This capability is particularly relevant for advancing the decarbonization of the maritime industry, especially in port operations, by offering a cost-effective, technologically innovative, and data-driven solution. Beyond its immediate operational benefits, the study contributes to the development of national solutions that enhance the technological capacity and competitiveness of the Brazilian

naval industry. Furthermore, by aligning domestic port operations with global sustainability objectives, this research supports Brazil in adopting environmentally responsible strategies, promoting both economic growth and the achievement of international climate and decarbonization goals.

2 Methodology

The methodology proposed in this study is based on the integration of Automatic Identification System (AIS) data, vessel characteristics, and fuel consumption parameters to estimate the energy demand of ships operating in the study area (Port of Rio de Janeiro). Based on these results, an estimation of the onshore energy supply required to meet vessel demand is also proposed. The general framework is shown in Figure 6, which summarizes the main steps of the process.

Figure 6: General framework of the proposed methodology for estimating vessel energy requirement in MJ.

2.1 AIS Data

As illustrated in the diagram, the methodology starts with the acquisition of AIS data through antennas, which are then stored in a dedicated database. For this purpose, an AIS receiving antenna was installed on the rooftop of Block A of the Center of Technology (CT) at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ). This antenna captures the signals transmitted by vessels

navigating in Guanabara Bay, and the information is stored in a dedicated server. These data constitute the basis of the study, as they are essential for analyzing the energy demand of the defined areas within the region.

Figure 7: AIS message reception frequency (daily average) from vessels in Guanabara Bay.

Figure 7 presents the frequency of AIS messages received by the antenna over a one-year period. The data are separated into Class A and Class B position reports, in addition to the total number of AIS messages. It can be observed that most of the messages come from Class A transponders, which correspond to larger commercial vessels operating in the bay.

2.2 SQL consulting

A SQL query system was applied to filter and organize the information, including spatial constraints defined by location polygons, in the same way as performed in Cepeda et al. (2018). For this project, AIS data transmissions were queried for vessels entering five predefined areas within the Port of Rio de Janeiro as can be seen in Figure 8.

The initial filtering stage applies a spatial query to isolate AIS messages where a vessel's coordinates (latitude and longitude) fall within the boundaries of any of these five terminals. The primary purpose of this first filter was to perform a coarse-grained selection, discarding all data related to vessels that were navigating outside the areas of interest, thereby significantly reducing the volume of the data set for subsequent processing. It is important to note that this step only verifies the presence within a terminal polygon and does not yet distinguish between different terminals or perform any vessel-specific analysis. The areas correspond to the main terminals of the port and were delimited by geographic polygons using the coordinates in Table 1.

This filtering procedure allows the isolation

Figure 8: AIS messages received in the five defined terminals of the Port of Rio de Janeiro. From July 28th of 2025 to August 18th of 2025. These AIS messages were of the following types: 1) type 1: class A position report accounted for 177,714 messages. 2) type 3: class A - Special position report accounted for 35,634 messages. 3) type 18: Standard Class B position report accounted for 23,958 messages. 4) type 21: Buoy sending position accounted for 23,284 messages. 5) type 27: Long range AIS Broadcast Message accounted for 468 messages.

of vessel traffic specifically associated with these terminals, enabling the estimation of their corresponding energy demand within the Port of Rio de Janeiro.

In this study, the AIS data underwent a systematic filtering and processing workflow to ensure consistency and accuracy prior to analysis. The raw data consisted of NMEA messages stored in a PostgreSQL database, accompanied by metadata related to the capture process. Initially, the dataset was queried by applying filters based on the receiving antenna and the observation period, thereby restricting the scope to the spatial and temporal dimensions relevant to the port under investigation.

Following this extraction, the raw NMEA messages were decoded using the Python library `pyais`, which provides robust tools for handling AIS communication protocols. A critical step in this process was the treatment of multipart messages, which frequently occur in AIS transmissions when information exceeds the size limit of a single NMEA sentence. In such cases, two- or three-part messages were first reconstructed before decoding, with the fragments being grouped according to their NMEA sequence ID. This procedure ensured that the semantic integrity of the AIS messages was preserved and that no data loss occurred during the decoding stage.

Terminal	Vertex	Latitude	Longitude
1	1	22°52'23.4"S	43°12'07.8"W
1	2	22°52'27.2"S	43°11'59.4"W
1	3	22°52'49.8"S	43°12'34.8"W
1	4	22°52'54.3"S	43°12'27.0"W
2	1	22°52'53.6"S	43°12'37.0"W
2	2	22°52'57.1"S	43°12'30.4"W
2	3	22°53'17.0"S	43°12'52.6"W
2	4	22°53'11.5"S	43°12'56.8"W
3	1	22°53'14.5"S	43°12'49.8"W
3	2	22°53'16.7"S	43°12'53.8"W
3	3	22°53'47.5"S	43°12'30.5"W
3	4	22°53'48.5"S	43°12'37.3"W
4	1	22°53'46.0"S	43°12'27.8"W
4	2	22°53'40.2"S	43°12'32.0"W
4	3	22°53'23.5"S	43°11'51.7"W
4	4	22°53'29.0"S	43°11'48.3"W
5	1	22°53'29.3"S	43°11'44.1"W
5	2	22°53'22.0"S	43°11'46.3"W
5	3	22°53'31.5"S	43°10'48.5"W
5	4	22°53'42.1"S	43°10'51.7"W

Table 1: Terminals' coordinates and vertex of the Port of Rio de Janeiro employed to filter AIS data.

2.3 Filtering AIS messages

The initial dataset comprised a continuous stream of AIS messages from April 15, 2025, to August 18, 2025, with a focused analysis performed on the high-quality, gap-free period from July 28 to August 18, 2025. The decoded messages contained fields such as timestamp, message type, MMSI (Maritime Mobile Service Identity), and latitude/longitude coordinates. A filtering step was applied to retain only messages containing a valid MMSI identifier, discarding any incomplete or corrupted entries. After filtering, AIS messages received are shown in Figure 9, it is noticeable a substantial decrease in messages and coverage of the data. The large number of filtered messages is mainly due to the ship database used for identification. This database only includes vessels above 500 GT, which explains why certain sectors appear to have no AIS messages after filtering. These sectors typically correspond to shallower areas, unlike the deeper regions where messages are concentrated. The depth distribution is illustrated in Figure 10.

Subsequently, the data were spatially filtered and segregated by terminal. For each terminal, the AIS messages were grouped by unique MMSI to isolate the trajectory of each individual vessel. This per-vessel grouping was crucial to prevent data interleaving and to enable accurate, ship-specific analysis. Each vessel's trajectory was then cross-referenced with a comprehensive global vessel database from 2022, which contains technical characteristics such as beam, draft, length overall (LOA), main engine power, and auxiliary engine power. Vessels not present in this reference database were discarded, as their

Figure 9: AIS messages received in the five defined terminals of the Port of Rio de Janeiro after applying mmsi valid filter. From July 28th of 2025 to August 18th of 2025. These AIS messages were of the following types: 1) type 1: class A position report accounted for 6,750 messages. 2) type 3: class A - Special position report accounted for 9,854 messages.

Figure 10: Nautic Chart of the Port of Rio de Janeiro showing the bathymetry of the areas of study.

technical specifications—essential for calculating energy consumption—were unknown.

2.4 Ship’s Energy demand

For each successfully identified vessel, its AIS-derived trajectory was enriched with vessel particulars (technical specifications). The time and distance between consecutive AIS points were calculated to derive instantaneous speed. This enriched dataset was then fed into a dedicated Consumption Module.

The module analyzes these processed trajectories to identify each ship’s precise entry and exit points for designated areas and determine its dwell time. Then, it integrates the vessel-specific engine power data and fuel characteristics (e.g., specific fuel oil consumption) to calculate the en-

ergy consumption associated with auxiliary engine operation during the vessel’s stay. By aggregating the calculated fuel consumption over time, the module provides a standardized output of hourly energy demand, suitable for subsequent analysis of energy requirements during port stays. In this way, the module can accurately estimate the energy consumed by each vessel in each studied area. Based on these results, it can infer the potential energy demand that could be supplied—for instance, through onshore infrastructure—allowing for the replacement of fossil-fuel-powered auxiliary engines and supporting strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

2.5 Fuel consumption module

The fuel consumption estimation was implemented through a model that combines vessel operational data with empirical correlations for main and auxiliary engines, as described in Cop (2024). The procedure takes as input the AIS-derived vessel speed, engine characteristics (MCR and service speed), and fuel properties (lower heating values, LHV). From these inputs, the model performs the following steps:

Distance The traveled distance between the two AIS points is computed using the great-circle formula (Equation 5), where R is the Earth’s radius, φ_1, φ_2 are the latitudes and λ_1, λ_2 the longitudes of the two points (in radians).

$$d = 2R \arcsin \left(\sqrt{\sin^2 \left(\frac{\varphi_2 - \varphi_1}{2} \right) + \cos(\varphi_1) \cos(\varphi_2) \sin^2 \left(\frac{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1}{2} \right)} \right) \quad (5)$$

Time The voyage time is obtained from the difference between two consecutive AIS timestamps.

Mean speed And the mean speed is obtained using Equation 6, where d is the distance between two ais positions and t_{travel} is the voyage time between two ais points.

$$v_{mean} = \frac{d}{t_{travel}}, \quad (6)$$

2.5.1 Main engine consumption.

To estimate the main engine fuel consumption, both AIS data and fuel data are required. First, the relative speed (V_{per}) is calculated using Equation 7, where V_{mean} is the mean speed previously obtained and V_{ser} is the service speed.

$$V_{per} = \frac{V_{mean}}{V_{ser}} \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

Next, the relative operational power is determined with Equation 8, modeled as a cubic function of the vessel's relative speed (V_{per}). Here, P_{csr} corresponds to 85% of the maximum continuous rating (MCR).

$$P_{per} = \left(\frac{V_{per}}{100}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{P_{csr}}{MCR} \cdot 100 \quad (8)$$

Subsequently, the specific fuel oil consumption (SFOC) in [g/kWh] is obtained as a function of the daily fuel consumption at service load, m_{CSR} [ton/day], as shown in Equation 9.

$$SFOC = \frac{100,000}{24} \cdot \frac{m_{CSR}}{P_{csr}} \quad (9)$$

The daily fuel consumption, m_A [ton/day], is then calculated using Equation 10. The total fuel consumption of the main engine, M_A , is obtained with Equation 11, where t is the time in days between two consecutive AIS timestamps.

$$m_A = \frac{24}{10^8} \cdot SFOC P_{per} MCR \quad (10)$$

$$M_A = 1000 m_A \cdot t \quad (11)$$

Since the focus of this study is on the vessel's energy demand, the calculated fuel consumption is converted into energy by applying the lower calorific value (LHV) of the fuel, as shown in Equation 12. The main engine fuel considered is heavy fuel oil, with an LHV of 39.96 [MJ/kg].

$$M_{A,energy} = M_A \cdot LHV_{kg} \quad (12)$$

2.5.2 Auxiliary engine consumption

First, according to Cop (2024), the required auxiliary engine power is estimated as a function of the main engine's maximum continuous rating (MCR), as shown in Equation 13.

$$P_{AE} = \begin{cases} 0.0025 \cdot MCR + 250 & \text{if } MCR \geq 10,000 \\ 0.05 \cdot MCR & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Next, the daily fuel consumption of the auxiliary engines, m_{AE} [ton/day], is calculated using Equation 14, where the specific fuel oil consumption $SFOC_{AE}$ is assumed constant at 215 [g/kWh].

$$m_{AE} = \frac{24}{10^8} \cdot P_{AE} SFOC_{AE} \quad (14)$$

In addition, blower operation must be considered. The blowers supply combustion air to

the auxiliary engines during start-up or at low load conditions. Their contribution is estimated using Equation 15 whenever the relative operational power P_{per} falls below 35%. In this case, m is calculated according to Equation 16.

$$m_{blower} = 0.02573 P_{per}^{0.6535} m \quad (15)$$

$$m = m_{CSR} \left(\frac{V_{per}}{100}\right)^3 \quad (16)$$

The total fuel consumption of the auxiliary engines, M_{AE} , is obtained with Equation 17. As with the main engine, this fuel consumption is converted into energy demand using the fuel's lower calorific value. For auxiliary engines, marine diesel oil is assumed, with an LHV of 42.1 [MJ/kg].

$$M_{AE} = 1000 (m_{AE} + m_{blower}) \cdot t \quad (17)$$

2.6 Port's energy demand

The model outputs energy demand for both main and auxiliary engines. These results are linked back to the vessel database to provide a consistent energy demand estimation framework.

The estimation of energy demand is presented through comparative analysis across port terminals, utilizing Python's scientific visualization stack (Matplotlib, Seaborn, and Pandas) for generating comprehensive graphical representations. This approach enables clear visualization of temporal demand variations, highlighting fluctuations associated with different vessel profiles, operational schedules, and waiting times at berth.

Since vessel energy requirements are inherently dynamic, demand is modeled as a time-variable quantity. However, within this variability, it is essential to establish a reference baseline: a minimum demand level that must be continuously guaranteed by the port infrastructure. This minimum value represents the lowest amount of power that needs to be supplied on-shore to ensure that vessels in waiting conditions can maintain essential auxiliary systems without resorting to their own engines.

To determine this critical threshold, we employed a comprehensive risk-based statistical methodology rather than relying on a simple absolute minimum, which would carry unacceptable operational risks. Multiple statistical approaches were evaluated:

- **Absolute minimum** of historical consumption data
- **5th percentile** approach (low-risk conservative strategy)

- **10th percentile** approach (moderate-risk balanced strategy)
- **Mean minus one standard deviation** (statistical normality-based approach)
- **Average of 5 lowest consumption days** (conservative smoothing method)
- **Minimum with 10% safety margin** (engineered safety factor approach)

The selected minimum demand value corresponds to the **10th percentile** of historical consumption data, representing an optimal balance between infrastructure investment costs and operational reliability. This approach results in an estimated energy shortage risk of approximately 10.5% of days (calculated as the percentage of historical days where consumption fell below this threshold), which was considered acceptable for port operations while avoiding excessive infrastructure oversizing. The visualization methodology included:

- Time series analysis with dual-scale plots to accommodate different terminal consumption patterns
- Comparative bar charts between main and auxiliary engine consumption
- Proportional energy distribution analysis using pie charts
- Hourly consumption pattern visualization across terminals
- Heatmaps for temporal-spatial consumption analysis

Therefore, the analysis not only captures the dynamic nature of energy consumption, but also defines, through a rigorous statistical risk assessment, the fundamental threshold that the port infrastructure must provide in a continuous and reliable manner to support decarbonization efforts through integration of shore power.

3 Discussion of results

3.1 Energy Consumption Analysis by Engine Type

The analysis of the total energy consumption across all terminals reveals a significant disparity between the power demands of the main and auxiliary engines. As illustrated in Figure 11, auxiliary engines were responsible for the vast majority (94.1%) of the total energy consumption during port stays. In contrast, the main

Figure 11: Proportion of total energy consumption of main(Blue) and auxiliary(Orange) engines during vessel port stays across all analyzed terminals.

engines accounted for only (5.9%) of the total energy used.

The predominance of auxiliary engine consumption is not just an aggregate effect but is consistently observed at the individual terminal level. Figure 12 provides a detailed breakdown of the average energy consumption per vessel call, clearly showing that the energy demand from auxiliary engines (shown in orange) vastly exceeds that of the main engines (shown in blue) at every single terminal analyzed (Terminals 1, 2, 4, and 5).

Figure 12: Comparison of average energy consumption per vessel call between main and auxiliary engines for individual terminals.

This consistent pattern across all terminals starkly highlights the role of auxiliary engines as the primary source of energy demand—and consequently, emissions—while vessels are berthed. These engines are typically kept running to

power vital onboard systems such as lighting, cooling, communication, and cargo handling equipment.

The findings from both figures strongly reinforce the thesis of this work: that providing shore-side electricity (cold ironing or Onshore Power Supply – OPS) is a critical and effective strategy for decarbonizing port operations. By allowing vessels to shut down their auxiliary engines and connect to the local electrical grid, ports can directly address this main source of in-port emissions, leading to substantial reductions in greenhouse gases and pollutants locally. Beyond this operational benefit, the main advantage of the proposed tool is the ability to quantify these emissions with precision, providing a robust basis for evaluating the impact of OPS implementation. The data underscores that targeting auxiliary engine operation through OPS would mitigate the most significant portion of a vessel’s energy footprint during its stay, a conclusion that is universally applicable across all terminals in the study.

3.2 Comparative Analysis of Terminal Energy Demand

To enable simultaneous visualization of energy consumption patterns across all terminals despite their significantly different consumption scales, the data was plotted using a logarithmic scale (Figure 13). This transformation allows for meaningful comparison of relative consumption patterns rather than absolute values, revealing several important insights into terminal operations.

Figure 13: Total energy consumption across all terminals using logarithmic scale for comparative visualization.

The logarithmic visualization reveals several key findings:

1. Significant Scale Differences and Data Considerations: The analysis reveals a substantial discrepancy in energy consumption

magnitudes, with Terminal 1 demonstrating approximately one order of magnitude higher consumption compared to other terminals. While this may reflect genuine differences in operational intensity, several data related factors must be considered:

- **Short Sampling Period:** The analysis covers only a 3-week period (July 28 to August 18, 2025), which may not represent typical operations. Terminal 1 might have experienced larger vessels traffic during this specific interval, while other terminals may have been in lower activity phases.
- **Operational Context:** The concentration of energy-intensive vessels (e.g., refrigerated container ships, large bulk carriers) at Terminal 1 during this specific period could explain the elevated consumption levels, possibly due to specific scheduling patterns or cargo requirements.

2. Similar Temporal Patterns: Despite the magnitude differences, all terminals exhibit remarkably similar temporal consumption patterns. The parallel trajectories in logarithmic space suggest that external factors affecting energy demand, such as port scheduling practices, weather conditions, or working hours, impact all terminals proportionally, regardless of their size.

3. Proportional Variability: The similar amplitude of fluctuations across all terminals indicates that relative variability (coefficient of variation) is comparable. This suggests that operational uncertainties and demand fluctuations affect large and small terminals proportionally to their size, indicating consistent operational responses across the port facility.

This comparative analysis demonstrates that while absolute energy demands appear to vary significantly across terminals, the fundamental dynamics of port energy consumption follow consistent patterns. The magnitude differences observed between Terminal 1 and other facilities should be interpreted with caution due to the limited sampling period and potential data quality considerations. Further investigation with longer-term data and validation of measurement consistency across terminals would be necessary to confirm whether these consumption differences represent genuine operational patterns or temporary anomalies related to the specific study period.

3.3 Hourly Consumption Patterns Analysis

The temporal distribution of energy consumption across terminals is further detailed in the

heatmap analysis (Figure 14), which reveals distinct operational patterns and peak activity periods throughout the day.

Figure 14: Heatmap of energy consumption patterns by hour and terminal, showing temporal distribution of demand.

The heatmap analysis identifies specific peak activity hours for each terminal:

Terminal 1 demonstrates the highest energy consumption, with sustained elevated activity between 08:00-18:00 hours and a pronounced peak occurring around 14:00-16:00 hours. This pattern suggests continuous daytime operations with maximum intensity during afternoon hours.

Terminal 2 shows a bimodal distribution with primary peak activity between 10:00-15:00 hours and secondary elevated consumption around **20:00-22:00 hours**, indicating possible shift work or extended operational hours.

Terminal 4 exhibits concentrated peak consumption during 12:00-16:00 hours, with particularly high intensity around 14:00-15:00 hours, suggesting focused afternoon operations.

Terminal 5 displays a more distributed pattern with moderate consumption throughout daylight hours 08:00-18:00 and a subtle peak around 12:00-14:00 hours.

The consistent elevation of energy consumption across all terminals during 12:00-16:00 hours indicates synchronized port-wide peak activity during afternoon hours. Notably, all terminals show minimal energy usage during overnight hours 00:00-06:00, confirming reduced operational activity during this period.

These identified peak hours provide valuable insights for energy management strategies, suggesting that port-wide energy demand peaks consistently during afternoon hours, while nighttime periods offer potential for energy conservation measures.

3.4 Risk-Based Minimum Demand Scenarios

The risk analysis of minimum demand requirements (Figure 15) provides multiple implementation scenarios for port electrical infrastructure planning, each representing a different balance between investment cost and operational risk.

Figure 15: Multiple minimum demand scenarios based on different risk tolerance approaches, showing daily total demand and selected risk-based threshold.

The analysis presents several implementation scenarios:

1. Conservative Scenario (5th Percentile - 21,062 MJ): This approach would provide energy coverage for 95% of days, resulting in only 5% risk of energy shortage. While this offers high operational reliability, it represents significant infrastructure oversizing, potentially leading to unnecessary capital investment and underutilized capacity.

2. Balanced Scenario (10th Percentile - 37,914 MJ - SELECTED): This moderate-risk approach was selected as the optimal compromise, providing coverage for 89.5% of days with a 10.5% shortage risk. This scenario balances infrastructure costs with operational reliability, minimizing both oversizing costs and shortage risks.

3. Statistical Approach (Mean - 1σ - 73,496 MJ): This method, based on normal distribution assumptions, would provide coverage for approximately 84% of days. However, it may still represent excessive capacity for typical operations.

4. Absolute Minimum Scenario (6,285 MJ): While economically attractive due to minimal infrastructure requirements, this approach would result in energy shortages on approximately 40% of days, representing an operationally unacceptable risk level for continuous port operations.

The selected scenario (10th percentile - 37,914

MJ) establishes a minimum demand threshold that ensures reliable operation while accepting a moderate risk level. The variable demand area above this threshold represents the additional energy requirements that must be accommodated through flexible grid connections or temporary power solutions during high-demand periods.

This analysis provides port authorities with a decision-making framework for electrical infrastructure investment, allowing selection of appropriate risk tolerance levels based on operational requirements and financial constraints.

4 Conclusion

This study's principal innovation lies in its utilization of freely available Automatic Identification System (AIS) data, captured via a standard receiver antenna, to generate critical insights for port energy planning. By transforming this openly emitted data into a reliable model of auxiliary engine demand, we provide a low-cost, scalable methodology to support the decarbonization of port operations, applicable to both Brazilian and international ports. The application of our risk-based methodology to AIS-derived data yielded a strategically determined minimum energy demand of **37,914 MJ**, established at the 10th percentile. This value represents a significant elevation from the absolute historical minimum of 6,285 MJ, which constitutes an operational risk. By selecting the 10th percentile threshold, the model accepts a calculated shortage risk of **10.5%** of days, achieving an optimal balance between infrastructure cost (associated with higher thresholds like the mean minus one standard deviation at 73,496 MJ) and operational risk. The analysis of energy distribution, as detailed in Figure 4, provides conclusive evidence supporting the core thesis of this study. The data reveals a stark disparity in energy consumption: auxiliary engines are responsible for **94.1%** of the total energy demand, while main engines account for a mere **5.9%**. This overwhelming proportion definitively validates the hypothesis that the primary source of energy consumption and subsequent emissions from vessels during their hotelling phase (at berth or idle) stems from their auxiliary engines. Consequently, this finding critically redirects the focus for decarbonization efforts, underscoring that solutions like onshore power supply (OPS) or alternative energy sources for berthed vessels must target auxiliary engine operation to achieve significant environmental and efficiency gains. In conclusion, the findings of this study highlight the significant potential of the proposed ap-

proach to accelerate the decarbonization of port operations in Brazil. By adopting a cost-effective and scalable methodology based on open AIS data, the research provides a robust foundation for the integration of onshore power supply and other clean energy solutions, reinforcing Brazil's position at the forefront of sustainable maritime development. The precise quantification of auxiliary engine demand empowers port authorities and policymakers to make informed investments in green infrastructure, particularly onshore power supply systems, which directly target the primary source of emissions from vessels at berth. Adopting this data-driven, risk-based approach enables a pragmatic transition to low-carbon operations, balancing economic viability with environmental responsibility. Therefore, this framework not only serves as a practical tool for immediate implementation but also establishes a benchmark for sustainable port management, potentially catalyzing a broader transformation of the maritime sector in Brazil and beyond. However, throughout this study, we also faced some challenges. Among them were the loss of certain data, which created gaps and made it difficult to identify a continuous time interval with reliable samples. In addition, there were periods when components of our AIS data capture station either burned out or stopped functioning, requiring maintenance before data collection could resume. These setbacks increased the difficulty of establishing a consistent database for analysis. Looking ahead, we aim to improve the database used in this analysis by addressing these gaps, expanding the number of AIS data collection stations, and establishing agreements with institutions to enable data sharing. Furthermore, we are exploring methods to address missing data through artificial intelligence, as highlighted in the literature review, and are committed to continuously developing visualization tools to enhance the analysis of fuel demand. Future research should expand on the present findings by improving the AIS data collection network, addressing data gaps through advanced imputation methods, and integrating artificial intelligence to enhance the accuracy of energy demand and emission estimates. In addition, future studies could evaluate the operational feasibility of onshore power supply (OPS) under different port configurations, assess the economic trade-offs of alternative clean energy solutions, and develop interactive visualization tools to support decision-making. These directions will strengthen the applicability of the proposed methodology and further advance the sustainable transition of port operations.

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